

L'Hopital's Rule for $q=1$ for Tsallis and Renyi Entropies and the Notion of Integration

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Both Tsallis and Renyi expressions contain the factor $1/(1-q)$ such that when $q \rightarrow 1$, $1-q \rightarrow 0$. The numerator also becomes zero, suggesting the use of l'Hopital's rule to find the limit which then yields Shannon's entropy. Both Tsallis and Renyi entropies use terms $f(e_i)$ power q which physically imply an AND product used to create a new probability. One may ask: Why is l'Hopital's rule required when one sets $q=1$? If one has f_i power q and sets $q=1$, one obtains f_i which is the term appearing in Shannon's entropy. We suggest that in addition to an f_i power q , there is an implicit integration, so to speak, which affects q . Thus, to recover the $q=1$, one must take the q derivative. This is most clearly seen for the Tsallis case, which allows one to set $q=1$ at the integrand stage without any l'Hopital's rule usage. Alternatively, one may consider both Tsallis and Renyi entropies in terms of a function: $G(q + (1-q))$ and expand about $q=1$. $G(q=1) = 0$ (as it is the numerator of both Tsallis and Renyi entropies), but the first derivative d/dq yields Shannon's entropy which measures the maximum number of states with no notion of q , i.e. extra bias. Here $1-q$ measures that bias from 1 in f_i power q .

Tsallis and Renyi Entropies

We argue that it is curious that one is required to use l'Hopital's rule and essentially take d/dq of a function which is the main functional part of an entropy (Tsallis or Renyi) in order to obtain another entropy, namely Shannon's entropy. We suggest that there should be an interpretation for this process. First, we note that

$$\text{Tsallis entropy} = \frac{1}{1-q} \sum_i (1 - \sum_i f_i^q) \quad ((1a))$$

$$\text{Renyi entropy} = \frac{1}{1-q} \ln \left(\sum_i f_i^q \right) \quad ((1b))$$

In both cases, the limit $q=1$ yields Shannon's entropy through the use of l'Hopital's Rule. One may note also that both approaches contain the factor $1/(1-q)$ suggesting a general function:

$$G(q + (1-q)) = G(q=1) + (1-q) \frac{dG}{dq} \text{ at } q=1 \quad ((2)) \quad \text{with } G(q=1)=0$$

In other words, one may note that f_i power q is a product probability in an AND situation and $q=1$ restores the f_i linear term associated with Shannon's entropy. ((2)) is an expansion about $q=1$, linked to the usual $f_i=f(e_i)$ linear term. The fact that $G(q=1)=0$ means that the $q=1$ case does not pick up any extra "entropy" due to a q factor and the second term in the expansion in ((2)) describes the already existing entropy associated with $f(e_i)$, i.e. the linear Shannon's term.

Thus, Tsallis and Renyi entropies are:

$$G(q) / (1-q) \quad ((3))$$

in order to pick up the extra entropy due to q as well as the f_i linear entropy associated with Shannon's entropy, we argue.

Tsallis Entropy and Integration

Tsallis entropy and the $q=1$ case may be seen more clearly because it may be formulated directly in terms of two body time reversal balanced elastic scattering, like Shannon's entropy, we argue. We first consider the Shannon case:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((4b))$$

Instead of taking \ln of ((4b)) to convert it into sums which may be matched with ((4a)), multiplied by the constant $-1/T$, we use a differential approach, already used in a previous note. We take the differential of ((4b)) and divide by the function itself creating terms:

$$df(e_i) / f(e_i) \quad ((5))$$

One may then integrate ((5)) from 1 to f to obtain $\ln(f(e_i))$. Then Shannon's entropy is minus the average value of $\ln(f(e_i))$, i.e.

$$S \text{ (Shannon)} = - \text{Sum over } i \text{ } f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i)) \quad ((6))$$

Tsallis entropy may be obtained in a similar manner except that one replaces ((4b)) with:

$$G(f(e_i)) \text{ such that } dG = df / f^q \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Integrating again from 1 to } f \text{ yields: } \{f^{(1-q)} - 1\} / (1-q) = \ln_q(f) \quad ((8))$$

(\ln_q is defined by ((8)).)

If one sets $q=1$ in ((7)) and integrates, one obtains $\ln(f)$, but if one first integrates to obtain ((8)) and then sets $q=1$ (removing the $1/(1-q)$ term, one does not obtain $\ln(f)$. To obtain $\ln(f)$, one must use l'Hopital's rule on the information ((8)) itself.

In other words, if q is present in the df expression, it is transformed through the integration. One must, in a sense, undo the integration to obtain the integrand and then set $q=1$. This, we argue, accounts for l'Hopital's rule being present in the Tsallis case for $q=1$.

$$\text{The Tsallis entropy is: } \text{Sum over } i \text{ } f_i^q \{f_i^{(1-q)} - 1\} / (1-q) \quad ((9))$$

The derivative of the numerator with respect to q followed by setting $q=1$ yields minus Shannon's entropy. One may also note, however, that:

$$d/dq \{f^{(1-q)} - 1\} = f^{-q} \text{ which yields the factor of } df \text{ in expression } d\ln(G) = df f^{-q}. \quad ((10))$$

Alternatively, one may apply l'Hopital's rule to ((8)) directly, yielding: $-1 / ((1-q) f^{\text{power } -q})$. This shows the need for an extra factor of $1/(1-q)$ to remove $1-q$ before setting $q=1$ and integrating.

Thus, d/dq has an effect of undoing the integral because $f^{\text{power } q} \int df f^{\text{power } q}$ is $f \ln f$ if one sets $q=1$ in $f^{\text{power } q}$ and in the integrand before integrating.

Conclusion

As a result, we suggest that the notion of using l'Hopital's rule for both Tsallis and Renyi entropies in order to obtain Shannon's entropy indicates that there is something other than simply an AND product $f_i^{\text{power } q}$ at hand. As seen in the Shannon's case, one may obtain information, $\ln(f(e_i))$, through integration of df / f . If f becomes associated with $f^{\text{power } q}$, then setting $q=1$ in the integrand is fine, but after the integral is performed one has l'Hopital's rule or must consider a d/dq derivative to undo, so to speak, the effects of the integration before setting $q=1$.

For both the Renyi and Tsallis cases, one may consider the numerator of the entropies as $G(q + (1-q))$ and expand about $q=1$. In such a case, $G(q=1) = 0$ because there is no q induced entropy, but there is still the regular Shannon's $q=1$, f_i linear form entropy given by the second term in the expansion, $(1-q) dG/dq$ at $q=1$ if one removes $1-q$.